

Fishing for Litter as a solution to marine litter in the Southeast Mediterranean Sea

A study into the predominant determinants of fishers' willingness to
participate in a Fishing for Litter program on the island of Crete

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Ioannis Schoinarakis

Student number: 2701267

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1st Supervisor: Pieter J.H. van Beukering

2nd Supervisor: Lotte van Oosterhout

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Institute for environmental studies (IVM)

Abstract

Marine plastic is set to double from 2010 to 2025, from approximately 8 million metric tons in 2010 to 16 million in 2025. The increasing numbers unveil the weaknesses of the global marine governance while they call for the appropriation of any available tool there is. Fishing for Litter (FFL) is one of those tools that can cost-efficiently bring positive change in the current situation. FFL is a program that provides bags to fishing vessels to collect litter that gets tangled in their nets during fishing activities. The collected litter is then disposed of appropriately at the designated docks. The following research aims to identify the factors that affect fishermen's motivation to participate in an FFL scheme on the island of Crete in Greece. Pro-environmental fishing behaviours in the southeast part of the Mediterranean have not been thoroughly studied. To do so, a face-to-face survey was conducted on local fishers (n=77) spread out in three different regions of the island. Respondents presented a high willingness to participate (87%) as almost all of them stated that they are familiar with the issue and struggle daily with marine litter related issues. In addition, fishers stated what urges them and what prevents them from participating in the scheme and listed what they need from the program to incentivise their participation. This paper ultimately formulates recommendations for a potential FFL scheme to be more effective and adaptive to local needs. Those recommendations can also be applied to other parts of the world that present similar social and geographical characteristics.

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1. Introduction

Marine litter is continuously increasing as a global problem affecting both the marine and the coastal environment. The complexity in terms of its sources and the impact marine litter entails have alerted the global community leading to numerous global, national and regional agreements to address the issue (UNEP, 2015). The entanglement of marine species, especially turtles, fish, mammals and birds, in marine debris is considered a severe mortality factor. Ingestion (mainly plastics) is also a crucial issue with unknown consequences to marine life and subsequently to human wellbeing (Katsavenakis *et al.*, 2004). From another perspective, marine litter is also creating problems for the fishing industry by damaging fishing vessels and their equipment (Brouwer *et al.*, 2015). According to UNEP (2009, p.13), marine litter is defined as “any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment”. Originating from land-based and sea-based activities, marine litter is perceived as a result of the lack of the public’s knowledge of co-responsibility (UNEP, 2015).

One of the actions to address marine litter is the Fishing for Litter (FFL) program. FFL is a community-based approach that aims to incentivise fishers to participate in marine litter collection. The logic behind the program is that debris entangled in the fishers’ net during their normal fishing activities must be collected and reported. That means that the findings must be placed in litter bags specifically distributed for the FFL program to be escorted to land for disposal. The main aims of the program are:

- Raising awareness of the fishing industry and changing the waste management practices of the sector,
- The removal of marine litter and the recording of litter resulting from the fishing activity (Aga *et al.*, 2020).

It has been reported that fishers are dropping or losing a significant amount of fishing gear in the sea, contributing to the problem. At the same time, they can only reach remote polluted areas that would otherwise be neglected (Veiga *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, FFL does not request any particular change in the fishing process, while it demonstrates success in collecting marine debris and educating the fishing industry. For these reasons, it is considered cost-effective (Morishige, 2010). Additionally, according to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive 2008/56/CE (2008), European governments have recognised it as a method that could help to achieve a Good Environmental Status (GES) in the European seas by 2020.

Currently, one can come across several global efforts to mitigate marine litter and its impacts. There are some worldwide initiatives such as the Global Partnership on Marine Litter (GPML), the Honolulu strategy, as well as the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD).

Moreover, four of the SDGs have targets relevant to marine plastic pollution, focusing on prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse, and sustainable management of the oceans (Löhr *et al.*, 2017). Even though FFL is one of the outcomes of those continuous efforts for marine protection, it seems that just the scheme's implementation is not enough.

There is an underlying necessity to understand the reasons behind fishers' participation to assure the success and longevity of the FFL schemes around the world. Efforts have been made to achieve that in countries like the Netherlands or the UK (De Boer, 2019; Wyles *et al.*, 2019), but no such assessment is available for Crete or the broader area of Greece. Having a very large fleet (14,018 as at

31 December 2019) engaging in fishing coastal stocks (Hellenic Republic Ministry of Rural Development and Food, 2019) Greece presents the potential for the appropriation of the fishing sector in the protection of the sea. The insight of fishers and the factors that can lead them to support such endeavours can potentially prove that point. For this reason, this study aims to investigate which factors can potentially motivate fishers to participate in an FFL program, how do different behavioural and external factors affect their will for participation and the role of the geographical characteristics of an island in their decision. The latter refers to the geographical scope of the research, which is the Greek island, Crete. The outcome of this investigation can be helpful for the guidance of already implemented FFL schemes or any upcoming ones. Understanding the motivations of the key actors in this program is essential for the successful expansion of this endeavour across the globe. Furthermore, investigating an island terrain can be of further use since remote islands can be more successfully reached by the program due to their small size and, therefore remote litter that affects neglected marine areas. For the reasons mentioned above, the question that this research intends to answer is:

“What are the factors that motivate fishers to participate in a Fishing for Litter program in the island of Crete, Greece?”

In order to answer this main research question, the following sub-research questions need to be examined:

- 1. “To what extent do fishers value local environmental status, and what is their share to its current state?”***
- 2. “How do the relation with local authorities and trust in others affect the decision to participate?”***
- 3. “How do the geographical characteristics of an island affect fishers' willingness to participate in a fishing for litter program?”***

Fishers' perception about the FFL needs to be understood and assessed to answer the questions above, and the most motivating factors will try to be detected to boost potential project uptake. The answers from these two tasks can significantly increase the expansion of the FFL program.

This research project will start with a literature review of the global initiatives for marine protection and will continue presenting the related theories that will contribute to answering the main and sub-questions of this study. Then the methodology section will thoroughly explain how the data for this research will be acquired. The field research part will consist of two methods, semi-structured interviews and survey, that are ultimately combined into face-to-face surveys to adapt to the sample's needs and characteristics. Once the data are collected, the results from the interview and the survey will be presented. Following the results, the conclusion part will answer the research question. Finally, policy recommendations will be presented to be used for similar future marine protection initiatives.

2.Literature review

Anthropogenic litter is present in all marine habitats, from beaches to the ocean's most remote points. On the seafloor, marine litter, particularly plastic, can accumulate in high densities with deleterious consequences for its inhabitants (Pham et al., 2014). From the perspective of environmental impacts, the history of marine litter research is interwoven with plastics' development. Global production of plastic has skyrocketed from around 5 million tons per year during the 1950s to over 280 million tons today (PlasticsEurope 2011). With this amount of raise, it is expected that many management strategies have been directed towards marine litter worldwide. Action plans and regulatory agreements such as the OSPAR convention have contributed significantly to reducing the inputs of plastic from land or sea-based sources to the marine environment (Ogunola et al., 2018). One of the most cost-effective and educational practices of OSPAR is the Fishing for Litter program. FFL became famous rapidly through the years as different regional and national initiatives can be observed around the world. In the Mediterranean, several projects are currently being implemented: Ecological bags on board (Spanish East Coast), Copuertos (Andalusian Coast, Spain), DeFishGear (Adriatic Sea), Port of San Remo (Ligurian Coast, Italy), Port of Rovinj (Northern Adriatic Sea, Croatia) (UNEP, 2015) and the iSea FFL (Northern Aegean Sea, Greece).

The waste that lies on the seafloor or floats in the water column is commonly captured by fishing nets, especially bottom trawl nets, and constitutes a variable part of fishers' daily catch. The FFL rationale is based on fishers disposing of these items at the port. The result is the removal of waste from the sea without the need for any extra costly action. The main assumption is that the activity must be as simple as possible for fishers and that it must not have direct or indirect costs for them. This initiative provides fishers with special bags to collect litter and ensures that disposal facilities are established and easy to access. The program's main aims are to clean the marine environment directly and raise awareness about the problem of marine litter amongst the fishing industry and the general public. This is intended to change attitudes and behaviour, all while providing data on seafloor litter (Ronchi *et al.*, 2019).

Regarding fisheries, the program has a lot to offer in economic aspects as well. Marine litter is causing fishers a loss of earnings due to time diverted to deal with marine litter encounters

and loss of earnings from reduced or contaminated catches resulting from marine litter ingestion or from equipment that continues to trap marine life even after they have been lost or dropped by the fishing vessels (ghost fishing).

Figure 1. A sea turtle entangled in ghost gear. Image: NOAA, Public Domain

More precisely, in the Eastern US, over 45 % of the commercial fishers had their propellers caught, over 30 % had their gear fouled, and almost 40 % had their engine cooling system clogged by plastic debris at some point in time (Wallace, 1990), this proves that marine litter can be a costly problem. Regarding contamination of fish and shellfish by microplastic ingestion, there has not been an economic assessment to estimate the costs of these effects so far. Nevertheless, evidence suggest that fisheries suffer losses, while the sustainability of the fish stock is affected (Newman, et al., 2015).

Following the steps of OSPAR and most specifically OSPAR Agreement 2017-081, iSea is the only organisation in Greece operating a Fishing for Litter program in the area at the moment. From October to December 2019, its first project was piloted in the Northern Aegean Sea, gathering more than 4.5 tons of litter from 8 trawl fishers. Their harvest was eventually weighted, collected, and recorded. In 2020 the project continued with the participation of 18 fishing vessels from the ports of Thessaloniki, Kavala, Alexandroupoli, and Volos. More than 17.3 tons of litter were weighted, collected, and recorded during the fishing season of 2020. According to the reports, most of the litter collected both years was plastic, ranging from 60 to more than 70%. The second most common source of waste was fishing equipment. As the program succeeds both in educating and averting costs to fishers as well as in environmental terms, there is a plan for expansion in 2021. Apart from the current ports, Heraklion, Lesvos,

Patra, Chania, and Chios will be the upcoming locations(iSea.gr), increasing the network and the influence of the organisation.

3.Theoretical Framework

3.1 Existing Theories

This research uses two different theories assessing human behaviour: The Theory of Planned Behaviour and The Value-Belief-Norm Theory.

The Theory of Planned Behaviour

One of the most renowned theories in psychology is that of Planned Behaviour (TPB) which was proposed for the first time by Icek Ajzen in 1985. The theory is meant to foresee and justify human behaviour in specific contexts. The concept is based on intentions. Intentions are believed to capture the motivational factors that influence behaviour; they indicate people's willingness to attempt to perform the behaviour. The basic rule is that high intentions eventually provoke action (Ajzen, 1991). Furthermore, it is admitted by the scientific community that behaviour depends at least to some extent on external factors like opportunities or resources, which are perceived as factors of actual control. However, it also depends on people's attitude and perception of their competence to actualise the behaviour of interest or their perceived behavioural control. According to TPB, people's perceived behavioural control combined with their intentions can be used to predict behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). Ajzen adds the subjective norm to those predictors, which refers to the social pressure individuals experience in terms of performing a behaviour or not. The significance of each predictor in the prediction of intention is likely to vary across behaviours and situations (Ajzen, 1991). In the case of FFL, the theory plays an important part in clarifying fishermen's behaviour, and it will constitute one of the main parts of the empirical basis for the research.

Figure 2. Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991)

The Value-Belief-Norm Theory

Figure 3. Schematic model of variables in the Value-Belief-Norm theory as applied to environmentalism, showing direct causal relationships between pairs of variables at adjacent causal levels. (Stern, 2000)

The value-belief-norm model (VBN; Stern, 2000) further develops Schwartz’s (1977) moral norm-activation theory of altruistic behaviour while it combines the Dunlap and Van Liere (1978) New Environmental Paradigm (NEP) theory to predict individuals’ level of support for the environmental movement. What Stern’s VBN theory does is that it postulates a causal chain of five variables that influence the types of action taken. Those variables are personal values, NEP, awareness of consequences (AC), the ascription of responsibility (AR) to self-beliefs, and personal norms (PN). The causal nature of the theory suggests that personal

values are defined as guiding principles, and it separates them into egoistic, altruistic and biospheric. This study plans to examine how personal values, AC, AR as well as the personal norms of fishermen can contribute to increase the uptake of a potential FFL in the study area. AC refers to whether someone is aware of the negative consequences of his/her actions, and AR refers to a person's feeling of responsibility for the negative consequences of acting or not acting in a pro-environmental way. Finally, PN refers to an individual's feeling of 'moral obligation to abstain or not from specific actions. Due to the critique the NEP received in the past as well as the doubling that occurs with the VBN and TPB theories, the content of the paradigm was decided not to be included in this research. The VBN theory has gained increased popularity between efforts trying to explain various environmental behaviours through psychology (Chen, 2015). It is believed that its application in this study might assist in predicting fishers' motivation to participate in an FFL program as well.

3.2 Conceptual Framework

The theories above were combined to formulate the conceptual framework of the research. As it is shown in Figure 3. they contribute in their way in the understanding of the determinants of fishers' motivation to participate in an FFL program. Those two's primary contribution is the perception of what forms fishers' pro-environmental intentions that ultimately lead to participation.

The theory of Stern (2000), The Value-Belief-Norm Theory, creates a chain-like causal relationship between variables that influence behaviour. In this case, fishers' values are separated into Egoistic, Altruistic and Biospheric. In this way, questions can be formulated to measure whether fishers are concerned about their personal resources (e.g., time, effort, space) or the quality of the fish they catch, whether they care about marine life and other people and whether they care about the sea itself, respectively. Those values combined with their willingness to change behaviour regarding marine litter are the guiding principles of the chain that form their awareness of the consequences of their actions which demonstrates whether fishers consider marine litter as a threat. Following the chain of VBN theory, their sense of responsibility accounts for their belief that their contribution can bring positive effects to marine health. The chain ends with creating the personal norm representing their sense of obligation to address the marine litter issue that ultimately leads to their actual intentions.

The Theory of Plan Behaviour will be utilised to help construct a more comprehensive idea of how to capture fishermen's behaviour. Ajzen (1991) is trying to prove that intentions are the ones that generate behaviours using a different rationale. Applying his findings in this research suggests that to understand fishers, one must study their attitude towards a healthier marine environment and the perception of their competence to achieve that while taking into account the social pressure they feel from colleagues or the society regarding making a change in the marine environment or not.

The TPB will be combined with the VBN theory as it has been done in previous research (Harland et al., 1999) to include the personal-norm concept while investigating behaviour for which moral considerations are likely to exist. The main objective is to gain insight into the contribution made by personal norms to understand behaviours beyond an explanation provided by the TPB in the environmental domain.

Some additional related variables might determine fishermen's scheme uptake that this research considers worth surveying. Some cultural traits of the profession and the island itself are being included in the investigation. Local pride, for example, is a factor that is being added to the scope of the research as the love and the feeling of deep pleasure or satisfaction derived from fishermen's origins might lead to increased participation in an effort to conserve their birthplace. This reasoning leads to the inclusion of the geographic characteristics of the island in the study. The sometimes-remote location of islands as well as their dependence or independence on the mainland might affect their environmental condition. With that in mind, fishers on the island might have an additional urge to protect something no one else will or contribute to a bigger problem like collecting litter that currents bring to their seas. In the case of Crete, which is located in the southern part of Greece, fishers might play a key role in collecting litter coming from the Aegean Sea right before it spreads to the rest of the Mediterranean. Finally, a cultural trait of the profession is the trust fishermen have in their colleagues and the local authorities. If they believe fellow fishers will fish for litter, then maybe they also will. Likewise, if they maintain good relations with local authorities, they might appear more willing to contribute to their society.

Figure 4. Conceptual framework (source: author)

4. Methodology

The most efficient way to understand the factors that can potentially motivate fishers to participate in an FFL program is to get in touch with them and analyse data deriving from their experience. For this reason, to answer the research question, a qualitative and a quantitative method are combined in this research. For the quantitative part, a survey is the primary method of data collection. It allows to reach a significant number of responses and, therefore, get a good idea of Cretan fisher's perception of marine litter. As for the qualitative data, due to the difficulty of approaching fishers for an interview, the survey was converted into a semi-structured interview where fishers opted in with additional information whenever they thought it was necessary or whenever they found it important to share more on a question. The conceptual framework has a crucial part in the execution of the field work; It was used to scientifically support the designing of the data collection process, namely the survey and the discussions that followed, by providing the scientific basis on which those were formed. To achieve that the variables of each theory were transformed into questions suitable for the purposes of this investigation (Appendix III).

4.1 Sample area

The sample area spreads around Crete. The investigation took place in the districts of Heraklion, Lassithi and Rethymnon. Because no location-specific database was found about the exact number of fishers on the island, the coast guard of each municipality was contacted telephonically to acquire this information. It was found that the current number of fishers on the island is approximately 908. The region of Heraklion reported 300 professionals, the region of Lassithi reported 158 professionals, Rethymnon 200 and Chania 250.

Regarding marine litter, previous research assessing the concentration of floating marine pollution in the region suggested that in the past, plastic concentration was in the range of 0–1160 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2$, a considerably low number. The mean pelagic tar concentration was the only one presenting an increase reaching 318 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2$, but even this number is not considered worrisome (Valavanidis, 2018). Unfortunately, no recent data was found to grasp the current situation of the Cretan marine environment. Therefore, the statements of the participants will be considered as a source to achieve that.

Figure 5. Map of the sample area (edited by the author)

4.2 Quantitative method

4.2.1 Survey

In terms of data collection, the survey is considered the primary source as it is shorter in time and does not require much physical contact, which at this time is hard to achieve due to the

COVID-19 pandemic situation. It should be mentioned that a premade survey is used in this investigation, provided by the research team of the Vrije Universiteit of Amsterdam. Modifications were made to reflect this study's conceptual framework, which was the base of the questionnaire. It consists of three main parts; Socio-demographics and background information about fishing, personal experience with and view on marine litter and willingness to participate in Fishing for Litter. The combination of Azjen's Theory of planned behaviour with Stern's Value, belief, norm theory significantly contributed to the design of those parts. Following these scientific principles is expected to bring robust and comprehensible results. Therefore, the final form of the survey was made by selecting questions from the premade questionnaire that directly connect to the framework's components. The addition of location-specific questions, such as local pride and fishers' feelings for the island, was one more modification that was done. Finally, an important aspect that was taken into consideration was the difficulty of talking to local fishers on the island because the research was conducted during their working hours. Subsequently, the survey was kept as short and comprehensive as possible. Various questioning techniques were selected to gather the data. From simple, short answer questions to Likert scales and ranking of options, the process was intended to be as interesting as possible to the participants. Upon completion, the survey was tested on five fishers to evaluate the validity of the results. A copy of the English version of the document can be found in Appendix I.

4.2.2 Sample strategy

To achieve a respectful amount of answers, the president of the association of professional fishers of each municipality was contacted to establish the first level of communication with the target area. In all cases, each president agreed to contact some of his colleagues, initiating a snowballing process. Similarly, fishers stationed in the port intended to help further by suggesting neighbouring boats to participate in the research. At this point, it is essential to mention that apart from contacting the president of each association, the rest of the sample was randomly picked and depended on the snowballing process. After the first contact through the phone, various trips were made around the island to reach the study areas. There, fishers were invited to participate in a student research to be convinced that this has nothing to do with politics or any other purpose that might disturb them. The majority of the fishers only wanted to participate when the survey questions were read out loud to them by the researcher, pleading that they lack the education to answer it themselves. In some cases, more than one fisher was surveyed simultaneously as the day's workload was a severe restriction; therefore, the questions were presented to the group. In this case, eye contact was intended with everyone, and each one was persistently asked to be attentive to keep them engaged and point out the importance of each answer.

4.2.3 Quantitative data analysis

The primary data of the survey was converted into a clean dataset and was analysed using SPSS 24 to obtain clear and presentable results of the sample area. The method used to

achieve that was descriptive statistics. Frequency tables and their visualisations (stack bars and pie charts) as well as assigning points to ranked answers to declare the most favourable one, were used to depict the opinion of Cretan fishers and their predominant motivations to participate in a project like Fishing for Litter. The dataset was mainly examined to provide beneficial information for the studied locations to anyone who might want to implement the project in one of Crete's numerous ports; hence, particular interest was shown in dividing the responses by different area. Additionally, this type of separation came together with the qualitative data collected that mainly reflected the reality fishers face in each location.

4.3 Qualitative method

The qualitative data collection paradoxically had to be changed due to the socio-cultural characteristics of the study area. The initial planning included a round of testing the survey while getting to understand the population of interest. This stage would ultimately provide insight into convincing fishers to give a semi-structured interview. As explained above, the surveying process was not the conventional one. Relatively early in the first stage of the research, it was understood that the best way to proceed was by combining qualitative interviews in the form of semi-structured informative dialogue with questionnaires as fishers perceived the process as such. The final data collection structure was face-to-face surveys as it was decided that it suits best the target population. According to the literature, face-to-face surveys allow the ability to collect more complex data while extending the survey's reach. The researcher can control the procedure and the environment by ensuring that the respondents attend to all questions without skipping any parts and asking questions to draw more information when necessary. In addition to that, it improves the response rate of the research since respondents do not feel the pressure of the formality of an interview. Finally, depending on their interest, they have partial control over the length of the procedure (Doyle, 2005).

Additionally, the semi-structured interviews were repeatedly denied and treated suspiciously, especially when the possibility of voice-recording for transcription purposes was mentioned. Consequently, the qualitative data were collected by notetaking. Most of the fishers chose to expand on questions that they found interesting while the questionnaire was being read to them, ultimately providing valuable information on local issues, their relationship with other fishers or even the local authorities or any other issue they found affecting their fishing activities. To process and then match this information with the quantitative data, summaries of the statements were made. Those summaries are used interpretively, which means that statements will be quoted at times while others will be presented more coherently. In this paper, the summaries are not included. Instead, Appendix II and Table 2 present a table of quotes from the participants that illustrates their overall views on the issues related to the research question. Some of those quotes will be used in the result section to support the quantitative findings.

5. Results

5.1 Sample analysis

The sample area spreads around the island, Crete. Most specifically, the district of Heraklion, Lassithi and Rethymno are contributing to the research accounting for most of the big fishing ports of the island. Starting from the district of Heraklion, 28 fishers are participating from the homonymous city, ten from the neighbouring municipality of Gazi and six from Hersonissos. In Lassithi, the ports of Agios Nikolaos and Ierapetra join the sample area with 24 answers, while in Rethymnon, nine fishers are participating (Figure 6). The locations mentioned above were selected to gather information from the most significant part of the island but also to include areas with different population density or geographical characteristics.

Sample distribution by Municipality

Figure 6. Pie chart the sample distribution divided by municipality.

Most of the fishers are between 35-70 years old (84% of the sample). 45% age from 50-70 while their educational level is low, from no education until high school. The majority operates as owners and captains of their boat (62%). That shows the way the fishing industry operates in Crete. Combined with the small sizes of the boats recorded, mostly smaller than 9.50 meters long, it demonstrates that Cretan fisheries consist of small individual efforts of family-run businesses. The most popular fishing technique is that of longline (57), while nets are used almost as much (55). Trawlers do exist, but according to respondents, their number is limited to 5 across the island. Longlines appear to be the most popular technique as it is not only used by professionals. Hobbyists use it as their only permitted fishing technique once they leave shore. Finally, fishing in Crete provides an average to low salary (<800€). Just below the average Greek cost of living, which is approximately 890€ per month (NUMBEO).

5.2 Personal experience with and view on marine litter

This section focuses on the personal experience fishers have with marine litter and their opinion on its potential effects on humans and the environment. The findings of the investigation recorded a general agreement on the environmental status of the island. Across all study areas, 90% of fishers declared that they had experienced issues on their boats due to marine litter, while 95% answered that they lose a significant amount of time to clean their boat and their equipment from marine litter. An agreement (81%) is also observed when asked whether they believe that marine litter is a reason for decreasing their catch (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Stack bars of fishers' personal experience with marine litter divided into three questions.

Additionally, the qualitative findings provide in-depth information that helps grasp the gravity of the situation at each location. For example, according to data from Heraklion, marine litter has to be addressed immediately. Fishers supported this statement with the following arguments: *"The situation in Heraklion is getting out of hand. I always let people know where I am when I fish because I had plastic clogging my propeller more than once."* (Table 2); *"People on the beach cannot really see it, but once you go out in the open sea, you can see huge piles of trash floating."*; *"Sometimes we lose good days of work just because we have to clean and repair our nets. Marine litter is affecting us in all sorts of ways."*; *"I have seen so much litter that I am afraid of the quality of the fish I catch."* (Appendix II). The small minority that disagreed with the questions above did not justify their answers, or even when they did; it seemed like they do not have the same perception of marine litter as the majority.

In other areas such as Hersonissos, people stated that the local infrastructure of rain-water disposal is that poor, that loads of litter end up in the sea and consequently on their boats and inside the fish people consume. In Irapetra, the passing trade boats and the numerous greenhouses built next to the shore, are polluting the sea with waste and plastic for years. In

Gazi, participants admitted that they had fished all sorts of items in the area, from umbrellas to furniture to vehicle parts, just to name a few. In Rethimno, fishers stated; “*Rethimno is a coastal city; thus, it suffers from the thoughtlessness of its citizens and tourism.*” In Agios Nikolaos, statements suggest that locals are more disrespectful to the sea than tourists who visit them due to their education gap (Table 2; Appendix II). Having said that, it is understandable why 91% of the participants consider marine litter a serious problem, and 66% see it as a reason for their decreased earnings. In terms of perceived risks of marine litter, as shown by figure 8, most fishers accept that the pollution mentioned above is inevitably affecting human health. Incidents of disagreement were recorded in the municipality of Hersonissos and Rethimno. In the first case, participants chose not to take a position as they believe that they do not possess the knowledge to answer the question. In the case of Rethimno, seven out of nine fishers do not believe that marine litter can directly affect human health.

Figure 8. Stack bars of the responses to the question; “Pollution’s effects on human health are worrisome” divided by municipality.

Finally, results prove that according to the awareness of fishers, it is believed that the fishing industry has different effects on the marine environment. To be more precise, the quantitative data provided in Figure 9 combined with participants’ statements suggest that opinions vary. Fishers in Heraklion have changed a lot in terms of environmental awareness in the past years. Twelve participants stated that they respect the sea; thus, they carry bags during fishing to collect their trash or whatever might stumble upon their nets instead of littering the sea and that many others do that as well. Nevertheless, the same number of participants stated that there is much room for improvement since the fishing culture lacks

education . A frequent complaint was that it is common to fish for abandoned nets that other fishers did not care to pick up during their fishing activities (Table 2). In Ierapetra, both quantitative and qualitative findings suggest that fishers contribute to the degradation of the marine environment. The inconsiderate actions of some have obscured the trust between locals. As a result, during the research, one could see people passing the blame for pollution. Statements like *“Do not trust what they tell you. People here do not even consider the environment.”* prove that (Table 2). Lastly, in Gazi, fishers acknowledge their wrongful actions, but they only seem to have reached this realisation recently as their lack of education did not allow them to understand the impact of their actions until their results were prominent (Table 2).

Figure 9. Stack bar of the responses to the question; *“Fishing industry is a source a pollution”* divided by municipality.

5.3 Participation in Fishing for Litter

Two questions were asked during the face-to-face survey interviews to draw conclusions about the willingness for participation. The first one was referring to the willingness of fishers to implement new techniques on their boats to participate in sea-cleaning activities. The question intends to measure the sample’s openness to change, and it is deliberately placed in the second part of the survey when respondents are not yet informed about the Fishing for Litter project. At that point, 64% responded positively, while the rest did not want to adopt new habits that might necessitate more effort from their side. An interesting case was that of Rethimno, where people were mainly negative (90%) while answering this question. According to their comments, new techniques were perceived as projects that some NGOs will probably implement. The previous experience of fishers with NGOs that did not fulfil their

promises made them suspicious over their actions and, therefore, over any upcoming suggestions for new projects implemented this way (Table 2). Upon reaching the third part of the survey, a short explanation of FFL was necessary to continue the process of questioning. After a few steps, a straightforward yes or no question about participation was asked (Appendix I). At that point, 87% of the participants agreed to participate in a potential FFL scheme.

Figure 10. (a) Responses to the question; "I am willing to implement new techniques", divided by municipality. (b) Responses to the question; "Would you participate in a potential FFL scheme in your area?" divided by municipality.

Furthermore, to understand where their will for participation stems from, the fishers that stated that they would participate in a potential scheme were asked to state why they would do so. In this case, the answers varied, with the most dominant (25%) being fishers' love for the sea and the island, and the second most favourable answer (18%) being "To contribute to the protection of the environment. An interesting case was that of Gazi, where participants unanimously declared that they are willing to participate, but all reasons to do so come second to financial compensation.

Main reason to participate

Figure 11. Pie chart of responses to the question; "What is your main reason to participate?".

5.4 Incentives to participate

To better understand the decisions of the sample, it was essential to investigate why they would abstain from a potential scheme. In this question, some respondents (19%) stated that collecting all that litter seems too time-consuming, while others (13%) stated that "There is not so much litter to bother participating in such a scheme." Contradicting as they might be, these two answers can be better understood when combined with some of the fishers' statements. For example, in Hersonissos, interviewees stated that the problem of marine litter in the open sea is not worrisome (Figure 8). Their main concern was the consequences of tourism in the area and the litter that accumulates on the beaches. On the other hand, interviewees in Ierapetra, Hersonissos and Heraklion (17%) stated that their profession is demanding as it is. There are plenty of tasks to complete every day, and therefore, it might be hard to incorporate more duties into their routines. In addition to that, some pointed out that Fishing for Litter does not match up with the responsibilities of fishing. Especially those interviewees who do not consider themselves as part of the problem believe that being the "cleaners" of the sea is not part of their job (Appendix II).

Figure 12. Stack bar of the responses to the question; “What is your main reason to abstain from the program?”

One of the main objectives of this research is to investigate what motivates fishers to participate in a scheme like Fishing for Litter; What do they want to obtain through participating, and what is the reason for their potential participation. To answer this, fishers were asked to rank on a scale from 1 (most important) to 4 (least important) the reasons that would convince them to take part in the project. As Table 1. indicates, the option “financial compensation per bag” is dominating in Crete.

Table 1. Scores of the reasons that would motivate fishers’ participation in a potential FFL scheme. Each answer was scored from 4 (most important reason) to 1 (least important reason). The table demonstrates the number of times the option was selected (N) as well as its summarised score and the percentage of points out of the total score for each option depending on the priority each fisher gave it.

“What would convince you to participate?”			
	N	Score	% Of score
In no case	2	8,00	1,6
Good instalments	27	87,00	17,6
Quality bags	13	34,00	6,9
Label	16	40,00	8,1
Good Cooperation	15	43,00	8,7
Promotion	12	32,00	6,5
Compensation per bag	67	250,00	50,6

Fishers truly value the financial reward. They indicated that they needed the extra money the scheme might bring, and it seems like the primary reason to overcome the burden of investing valuable time in the project or any other reason that will urge them to abstain. The following statements can reflect this; “ We need the extra money in order to bother cleaning. Our financial situation does not allow for voluntarism.”; “ I do not see why not to participate, but I need the extra money to keep on doing it on a steady basis.” Another explanation is that people are waiting for a motivating gesture to incentivise their efforts and trust the process as many projects have been intended in the area, but not many succeeded. A fisher in Heraklion stated: “ We need incentives to activate ourselves. Money is the most effective one.” While another participant in Hersonissos said: “ What fishers need is an incentive. Something that will get them started. It can be 5€ or 55€ per bag. The important thing is to get them started so that they can see what they can actually achieve if they try.” (Table 2; Appendix II). The data below also represent that. One can see that the majority of the answers were not a specified amount. Fishers are not looking for a price that will drastically change their income; they are looking for an amount that confirms that the project will stay, and it will change the Cretan fisheries mentality. Second, but significantly less important than the financial reward, came the necessity for good instalments at the ports where the project will take place. Some respondents mentioned that they expect good facilities in the port so that the program runs flawlessly, minimising the effort from their side (Table 2).

Desired amount per bag

Desired amount per bag	
Valid	70
Missing	7
Mean	34,21
Standard Deviation	39

Figure 13. Pie chart indicating fishers’ desired amount per bag of litter along with the frequency of each amount, the mean desired amount and the standard deviation of the answers.

5.5 Behavioural aspects of participation

Lastly, the respondents were asked a series of questions to understand whether a list of behavioural aspects can possibly affect their participation. As seen in Figure 14, those aspects

can relate to feelings, attitudes or norms that can provide additional information on fishers' motivations. In most cases, participants replied positively. The protection of the island and the rest of the Mediterranean Sea appear to be essential to them. A strong foundation of pro-environmental thinking and acting is observed as fishers agreed at a rate of approximately 90% that they feel a moral obligation to participate in a scheme like that and that collecting marine litter should be a norm in order to reverse the current situation. A noteworthy outcome is that more than half of the sample admitted that fishing is so time-consuming that it can be difficult for them to take up additional responsibilities such as collecting litter.

Figure 14. Stack bar charts of all the responses regarding behavioural aspects of participation

Table 2. Illustrative example of fishers' statements divided by study area. (Source: the author)

Heraklion	Gazi	Hersonissos	Ierapetra	Rethimnon	Agios Nikolaos
Marine litter in the area					
<i>"The situation in Heraklion is getting out of hand. I always let people know where I am when I fish because I had plastic clogging my propeller more than once."</i>	<i>"We used to treat the sea as an infinite landfill. We did not know. Now that we see the results, we are starting to change."</i>	<i>"This is a very touristic area. All the coast is filled with bars and restaurants that dispose of all their waste in the sea."</i>	<i>"Here, we mostly find litter coming from greenhouses and local people. Currents do not affect this part of the island. At least not in that way."</i>	<i>"Bars, restaurants and hotels are constantly polluting. The litter we catch can prove that."</i>	<i>"Locals are disrespectful to the sea. In comparison to the tourists that visit us, we lack education."</i>
Relationship with other fishers					
<i>"Sometimes, I get disappointed. I see people abandoning nets in the sea, and then others pay the price when the nets get stacked on their propellers."</i>	<i>"We are all friends here. It is some sort of protection. Imagine a rivalry in a port of 15 boats. That can not be good for us."</i>		<i>"Do not trust what they tell you. People here do not even consider the environment."</i>	<i>"We argue and we fight. I think it is because of the lack of education in this profession. Most fishers never went to school."</i>	<i>"There is a lot of competition between us as the stocks are constantly decreasing. It is getting so hard that even hobbyists are also damaging our earnings."</i>
Relationship with local authorities					
<i>"I would never appeal to local authorities to resolve an issue."</i>	<i>"We lack the necessary support. We have a small port that is very neglected."</i>		<i>"We have an excellent relationship with local authorities. They listen to our demands, and we listen to theirs."</i>	<i>"There is a lot of suspicion for NGOs. Everybody gets involved with the sea but with no outcome. So why would I trust them?"</i>	
Comments on Fishing for Litter					
<i>"We need incentives to activate ourselves. Money is the most effective one."</i>	<i>"If there is money involved, I am definitely participating in something like this."</i>	<i>"We prefer money for fuel as an incentive to participate."</i>	<i>"I know that many things that can come out of this, due to the injustice fishers face every day, money is the only reason to participate."</i>	<i>"We need good instalments. I do not want to waste time carrying trash around the port."</i>	<i>"I believe NGOs are lying to us, and therefore, I would prefer a project like this to be implemented by a different carrier."</i>

6. Discussion

The objective of the present research was to identify the predominant motivators for fishers to participate in the Fishing For Litter (FFL) scheme on the island of Crete. According to various sources (KIMO; Morishige, 2010; Aga et al., 2020.) FFL is a cost-effective approach that contributes to cleaner seas by reaching to litter in the open sea. This is the first study to

investigate fishers' key motivations to participate in an FFL scheme in Greece and, most specifically in the island Crete, aiming to provide guidelines for any potential project implementation. Precisely, qualitative and quantitative social research methods were applied to understand fishers' perception of the topic, and under which circumstances a potential project could fulfil their needs to increase its uptake. To achieve that, two different theories assessing human behaviour were utilised (Ajzen,1991; Stern, 2000) to ensure that the data collection part will include the necessary tools to collect sufficient and valid information to reach robust conclusions.

6.1 Willingness to participate

One of the main findings of this research was to grasp the overall acceptance rate of a potential FFL scheme on the island. The survey revealed that 87% of the participants are willing to participate in such an endeavour. An interesting addition is the difference reported between the willingness to implement new sea-cleaning techniques on their boats and the straightforward question of whether fishers would participate in an FFL scheme in the area or not (Figure 10). Even though both questions examine fishers' openness to change habits, the first one was asked before informing participants about the FFL. Comparing the results revealed that fishers have a particular interest in the program since more positive answers are observed when FFL is mentioned. In addition to that, the lack of information and knowledge might affect fishers' willingness to participate. Without a clear picture of how FFL works, participants appeared suspicious about the program since they felt it would bring a big change of habits. Nonetheless, to further understand the reason why the acceptance is that high, one should look into the associated factors that lead to those results.

6.2 Marine litter status and fishers' ascription of responsibility

Even though studies show that in the last decades, the importance of the pollution problems and their impacts on the coastal zones is relatively low in Crete (Valavanidis, 2018), the findings of this paper suggest that fishers do come across marine litter constantly during their time in the open sea. It is essential to this research that nearly all participants stated that marine litter is a threat to them, the environment, and, ultimately, their earnings. Evidently, the open sea of Crete is facing threats of different origins. Sewage mismanagement, tourism, overfishing and lack of environmental education, to name a few, have been reported. According to participants' statements, some are more prominent in the south and others on the north coast of Crete. The source of the problem depends on various local aspects and has to be investigated separately in each location.

Questions related to the current environmental pollution issues manifested how much respondents value the marine environment. As a matter of fact, fishers demonstrated a deep interest in the effects of pollution not only because it affects their earnings and the quality of the fish, but also because they are afraid of its worrisome consequences on human health. In

line with the findings of Ajaps (2015), these results suggest that more knowledge on environmental issues leads to higher appreciation for the environment. A noteworthy finding related to this topic is the array of opinions regarding the contribution of fisheries to marine pollution. The answers unveiled different stories in each location. Fishers from Heraklion, Hersonissos, Agios Nikolaos and Rethimnon, do not see themselves as a part of it. In line with scientific literature (Stern, 2000), due to their ascription of responsibility, fishers are steering towards a more conscious direction where their understanding of littering impacts leads them to take care of their waste and pick up trash on their way. Participants stated that being proactively thoughtful compared to past decades' inconsiderate behaviour is part of their routine now. Such a finding implies that fishers in those areas are one step closer to the project and that its implementation will be easier to facilitate since they have already integrated good practices into their daily work that are very similar to the program. On the other hand, Ierapetra and Gazi almost unanimously stated that they find themselves responsible for marine degradation. The lack of understanding of the consequences of their actions suggests a project that will focus on education as a tool to help locals understand the positive impact a clean environment will have on their profession and the wellbeing of the island as literature indicates (Ajaps, 2015).

6.3 Motivations

Apart from understanding the current situation on marine litter, the data collection, utilizing the insight provided by the theoretical framework (Ajzen 1991., Stern,2000), included questions that map behavioural aspects that might influence the scheme uptake.

From this type of questions (Figure 14), the most constructive results suggest that fishers in Crete foster strong feelings for the island and when it comes to its protection, a sense of obligation and pride motivate them to participate. This is also proven by the fact that the majority of respondents answered that the love for their birthplace and the protection of its environment are the main reasons that would urge them to participate. Furthermore, most participants agreed that collecting marine litter during fishing should be a norm that once again justifies the high acceptance of the project in the area.

Results also addressed the research question about how the geographical characteristics of Crete affect fishers' decision to participate. It was generally agreed that the island should take care of its own environment, which, according to qualitative evidence, is being attacked by pollution mostly at its northern coast. In addition to that, people seemed to understand that their responsibility increases due to the geographical position of Crete. More than 80% of participants agreed that if they do not take action, litter would spread to the rest of the Mediterranean Sea as literature on marine currents suggests (Poulain et al., 2012). Despite the general agreement presented by the quantitative data on this topic, the qualitative part of the face-to-face survey demonstrated a lack of interest from the respondents' side. It is therefore suggested that those results are considered with caution.

In addition to the behavioural aspects above, it was essential to understand what fishers expect from the program to adjust or improve any upcoming one. In contrast with the findings in the UK and the Netherlands (K. J. Wyles et al., 2019; de Boer 2019), where intrinsic motivations seem to affect the most fishers' decision to participate, Cretan fishers repeatedly stated that financial compensation is a precondition to participating. The combination of fishers stating that their monthly income is below the average (<890€) and the literature that states that income affects environmental awareness and pro-environmental behaviour (Philppsen et al., 2017), explain where this precondition stems from. The tough financial conditions fishers face will most likely not incentivise environmental sensitivities such as participation in the FFL. In addition to that, the opinion that money builds trust between the stakeholders was also dominant amongst participants.

Accordingly, fishers appear to expect an incentive that could provide a slight financial boost while showing that participants' efforts are respected. This is visible regardless of the location by respondents' urge to avoid declaring a desired amount per bag and ask for respectful compensation instead.

6.4 The effects relations with local authorities and trust in others have on participation.

The relations between stakeholders was the most location-specific finding of this research. Some of those findings were unexpected since they became visible once fishers started to feel more comfortable with the whole process of face-to-face surveying. Not as much variation was found in answers regarding the problems litter generates or the motivations for participation as it did when assessing the effect relations amongst fishers and authorities have in each area. It appears that any change in the sector strongly depends on what other fishers think or do and what role the authorities play in it. For example, respondents from Heraklion and Gazi expressed disbelief in local authorities and their actions and therefore were against any cooperation with them, while in Rethimnon, after an adverse history with Non-governmental environmental organisations in the area, fishers demonstrated an urge for rejection of any project implemented by this type of organisations. Having that said, it seems essential to select wisely the mediator that will take over the initial approach and the communication with the fishers. Ensuring that fishers accept and trust the facilitator with whom they will have regular contact is crucial to the scheme's uptake.

Regarding trust amongst fishers, the high competition that was reported in Heraklion, Ierapetra and Rethimnon also led to a lack of trust between them. This hostile atmosphere led fishers to copy each other and follow each others fishing path or techniques in order to increase their catch. In terms of FFL, this trend might have mixed results. On the one hand, the reported competition can actually be used in favour of the program since, according to the Theory of Planned Behaviour, the subjective norm of fishers might create just enough social pressure to make the less interested fishers to follow the more aware ones by

participating. On the other hand, one should keep in mind that hostility between stakeholders might also steer them in abstaining from the program (Ajzen, 1991). In areas like Gazi and Agios Nikolaos, reportedly, good relations between fishers can have similar effects and ultimately boost the scheme uptake. In these cases, the will for participation of one might positively affect the will of the others through deliberation and understanding. In both instances, social pressure can play a big part, whether it stems from following the steps of others due to cooperation or stiff competition.

Nevertheless, it is vital to keep in mind that good relations might bring better results in terms of imitation and willingness for participation, whilst hostility and competition can bring unwanted results. In contrast with the relation with authorities, fishers' relations is a factor that is out of the reach of the program. The way of approaching fishers and educating them about FFL might influence how they will perceive the value of participating in numbers, but it cannot assure that personal and professional differences will not drive them away.

6.5 Limitations

Considering the human dimension is key to resolving environmental issues, and conducting field research is most times necessary for one to do so. During this effort, this research faced various limitations that one should bear in mind before considering the robustness of its results.

For starters, the data collection was accomplished through face-to-face surveys. Even though this technique comes with many advantages, there is evidence that personal questions are less likely to be answered truthfully (Doyle, 2005). The loss of anonymity that appears due to the interviewer's presence affects the respondents, and therefore their answers are prone to the fear of presenting a less appealing side of themselves. This phenomenon is known as "social desirability bias" (Larson, 2019) and appears to have altered the responses for a part of the sample. Especially on questions regarding environmental protection, many chose to present themselves as sensitive and responsible shortly after they reported a high amount of pollution in the area and admitted that they and their colleagues are part of the marine pollution problem.

Another issue that arises through the data collection is the research environment and its ascribed implications. As already mentioned, the research was destined to be executed at the ports where fishers would be working on their boats shortly after their return from fishing. The setting of the port is usually crowded at those hours. Fishers would come and go, sometimes jumping into the conversation affecting the opinion of the participants. Along with that, younger fishers or less interested ones often agreed with the opinions of the previous respondent that they happened to overhear. Finally, since fishers were often occupied with work, they lacked focus, and the survey took too much time to complete. The outcome was rushed answers without reflections which hampered the collection of in-depth answers on specific topics. Similarly, on questions regarding geographical characteristics, it is unclear

whether fishers responded indifferently, just to complete the survey or because they genuinely agreed with the presented statements. This observation raised doubts about the adequacy of the questions concerning geographical characteristics and suggested that further research would be necessary to answer this research question more confidently.

In addition to that, the final size of the sample could be considered as a limitation. First of all, fishers as a social group are hard to approach due to various reasons. Their working hours, the harshness of their profession, the weather conditions, or their state of mind on the given day, to name a few, can play a big part in their willingness to participate in a survey and the responses they might give. Secondly, the current COVID-19 pandemic and the restrictions of movement implemented in Greece limited the data collection from covering the island's entirety and obliged the researcher to interrupt his investigation due to recurring authority controls. For these reasons, the sample size resulted relatively small and ultimately led to the decision of conducting a descriptive analysis of the quantitative results instead of running an analysis of variance that could help extrapolate the results to the broader population since the last necessitates a more significant sample to provide reliable outcomes (Field, 2013).

7. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, several suggestions can be given that can be used as guidelines for any future Fishing For Litter project on Crete. The quantitative and qualitative data collected contributed to creating a clear picture of the modifications needed to increase the scheme's uptake in each study area. Therefore, this section has two objectives; First, it aims to provide some general recommendations addressing fishers on all Crete. Second, it intends to respect the observed differences in opinions, threats and incentives for the participation of each port and give location-specific guidelines.

7.1 General Recommendations

The contact with the fishing industry on the island brought insight into the unspoken needs of fishers that can ultimately be translated into guidelines for implementing the FFL. For starters, one should consider the culture and history of the island and how important that may be to fishers; People admitted that they are proud of the island and are willing to sacrifice time and effort to protect it. In some cases, this attribute can overcome any other precondition. For example, an FFL project that campaigns for preserving the beauty and health of the island might encourage participation over any other preference fishers might present. Second, it is known that both governmental and non-governmental organisations that are occupied with matters related to the sea can implement the project. However, the scheme's uptake on the island highly depends on who will finally do that since each port presents different opinions about NGOs and local authorities. Third, an upcoming scheme might want to use education to increase participation and have consistent results. Almost every respondent mentioned that he lacks basic knowledge of marine issues and does not

realise the damage that the sea has suffered. A scheme that focuses on that can actually change how the fishing industry sees the sea and make participation a conscious choice for fishers. Fourth, the financial struggles of fishers have been going on for years, and therefore, it may be easier for a future FFL scheme to find financial solutions to increase participation. Nevertheless, a few alternatives will be given below to generally enhance participation and also make the implementation of the project feasible in case compensation is not possible.

Heraklion

According to participants, Heraklion is the biggest port on the island and therefore presents the highest number of fishers and the highest amount of litter. Due to this fact, fishers are already familiar with the marine problem and seem to suffer damages from it. This experience with marine pollution indicates that a project willing to tackle the issue can be welcome in the area. Additionally, fishers reported that they have started using bags to collect their trash on their own for years, creating a fertile ground for the FFL to flourish. Moreover, to counter the high demand for financial compensation, which might not align with the FFL's characteristics, the program can use the current environmental situation to promote participation. Fishers see the pollution affecting them but are not entirely familiar with its long-term consequences to their finances and human health. Communicating the benefits that the scheme brings might trigger the high sensibility fishers have for their land and change their source of motivation. An important particularity of the area that must be considered is the relations amongst fishers and the authorities. There is low to no trust in the local authorities, and previous incidents have steered fishers away from them. Therefore, any future program should attempt to minimise their involvement as it can crucially affect the cooperation between parties.

Gazi

The port of Gazi is situated just a few kilometres to the west of Heraklion. It is a small neglected port with only a few fishers that report having problems with marine litter as much as fishers in Heraklion did. The good relations amongst them can be of use to the program since convincing some fishers to participate might spill over into the rest. An obstacle to the uptake in this location is the precondition of financial compensation set by the fishers. This can be resolved in two ways; Firstly, since all fishers find themselves responsible for the state of pollution, the program can play the educator of the consequences of pollution and point out its benefits. Secondly, fishers might decide to participate as long as the program helps them with other problems they face. For example, if by catching, cleaning and recycling lost nets, the program can help fishers replenish the damage sea mammals do to their nets (Appendix II), then the lack of financial reward might not obstruct their participation anymore.

Hersonissos

Hersonissos is one of the most touristic areas on the northern coast of Crete. Only six boats practice fishing in the area. The primary source of pollution there comes from tourists and touristic facilities; therefore, most of the litter stays close to the shore, where local authorities can address the issue by recruiting a boat to clean local beaches or implementing new techniques to prevent litter from ending up in the sea. Even though FFL might not be a big success in the area due to the aforementioned, local fishers made a recommendation that can be applied to all locations in order to counter the need for financial compensation; Instead of using its own funds, local authorities or environmental NGOs can use the plastic bag tax to finance the project. In case the needed budget is too high, they also suggested providing a portion of fishers' fuel costs to show their good intentions.

Ierapetra

According to respondents, the sea in Ierapetra suffers from the inconsiderate habits of locals and the plethora of greenhouses situated there. As a result, many old plastic covers and chemicals are thrown in the sea only to end up in the fishing nets of local fishers or to wash up on the beaches. The competition is very high, and the fish stocks are almost depleted. Therefore, the FFL can bring real change in the area. In addition to reducing the marine pollution levels, the program can ameliorate the relationship amongst fishers who tend to blame each other for the local marine problems. By recording the marine litter, the impact of greenhouses can be pointed out, and the necessary proof can finally be gathered for the authorities to resolve the issue. In this way, the resolution of local problems might significantly increase the scheme's uptake. Moreover, fishers seem to be on good terms with the local authorities; hence, the introduction of the program is best to be done by them, addressing all fishers. This way, participation is likely to be higher, and no one will feel excluded. Finally, participants seem to be motivated by the idea of receiving compensation for their efforts. Once again, the financial difficulties steer respondents to this decision. If this is not possible, the scheme should focus on communicating that the program's benefits can increase fishers' earnings due to fewer accidents and maintenance without taking too much of their time.

Agios Nikolaos

In Agios Nikolaos, fishers stated that the primary source of pollution is the local population. Even though the area is considered very touristic, they suggest that locals show less respect than tourists to the sea. Considering this, along with the feelings fishers foster for their birthplace, a potential scheme should focus on how participants can differentiate themselves from the inconsiderate population and take action. On top of that, Agios Nikolaos is located in a gulf and therefore, the concentration of litter in the area is likely. Hence, its potential effects can be used as an argument to sensitise fishers and boost participation.

7.2 Future research

This paper also stimulates a need for further research to understand and delve into the elements that trigger fishers' pro-environmental behaviour. First, it is essential to focus on gathering more data and expanding to the entirety of the study area to identify the sample's needs and characteristics better. Moreover, a bigger sample might allow the extrapolation of the results to the rest of the fishing industry of the studied country or area by running an inferential statistics analysis. Second, future studies might want to investigate methods to form alternative incentives for fishers to take part in the FFL scheme. That way, a more economically feasible project can be designed. Third, the social desirability bias should be considered when forming the data collection method to assure the robustness of the study. Lastly, a crucial realisation during the fieldwork was the importance of the first contact with the potential participants. The fishing sector constitutes a relatively complex target group. The difficulty of the profession, its harsh and demanding conditions might affect the willingness of fishers to participate in a survey. Therefore, it is recommended to plan the surveying carefully as it can be vital to the response rate and, ultimately, to the sample size of any future research.

8. Conclusion

This research was the first to examine the predominant determinants of fishers' willingness to participate in an FFL scheme. Using mixed methods suitable for the given sample made it feasible to understand what incentivise Crete fishers to participate in a potential project. More precisely, the findings unveiled that fishers more than often face marine litter related issues which end up affecting their wellbeing in various ways. Being familiar with the problem, most respondents stated that they would participate in a potential scheme in the area and be part of the solution. Other prevalent results suggest that respondents foster strong feelings about their birthplace and value and care about the local environment, which are important indicators for pro-environmental behaviour.

Moreover, even though quantitative results showed that the island's geographical position is important to fishers since it is vital to protecting the rest of the Mediterranean Sea from marine litter, the lack of interest of the respondents during the face-to-face surveying suggests that those results might not be sufficiently robust. A profound investigation on those attributes might resolve this. Furthermore, whilst various alternatives might contribute to a successful FFL implementation in the study area, fishers concentrated on their profession's financial difficulties. Therefore, they selected financial compensation as the most suitable incentive that can guarantee high participation. Finally, an unexpected outcome of this research was how depended willingness for participation appeared to be on local relations. Whether that was interpersonal or relations with local authorities and organisations, it became evident that a potential scheme should consider this trait upon implementation to avoid obstructing participation.

These findings have practical implications on developing an FFL scheme on the island of Crete that can potentially be used as guidelines for other locations that present similar social and geographical characteristics. Additionally, it proves that social and behavioural sciences can offer insights and data that can help maximise the success of environmental interventions.

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Appendix

Appendix I

The following survey was implemented during the investigation:

FISHERY SURVEY

WHO ORGANISES THIS RESEARCH?

This survey is part of a research project of the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. If you have any questions regarding the study, please contact our researcher, Ioannis Schoinarakis, i.schoinarakis@student.vu.nl

Consent for participation in this survey

We are interested in the fishing community's thoughts on marine litter. Please note that there are no right or wrong answers in this survey, we are only interested in your opinion. The survey will take around 20 minutes to finish. All information that you provide in the questionnaire will be treated as strictly confidential. Your anonymity will also be safeguarded in any publication of the results of this research. You may freely choose to stop the survey at any time.

By pressing 'Yes' you agree to the above mentioned conditions and start the survey.

Yes

No, stop this survey

PART 1: ABOUT YOURSELF

1. What is your gender?

- Female
- Male

2. How old are you?

.....

3. What is your role on board?

- Captain and owner
- Owner (but not the captain)
 - Captain (but not the owner)
 - Engineer
 - Sailor
 - Other, namely

4. How much is the average monthly net salary (after tax deductions) of your household?

- Less than €500
- €500 - 649
- €650 - 799
- €800 - 949
- €950 – 1099
- €1100- 1250
- More than €1250
- Prefer not to say

5. I fish...:

- Professionally
- Non-professionally

6. In which municipality do you fish?

.....

PART 2: BACKGROUND INFORMATION ABOUT FISHING

FISHING TECHNIQUES

7. Which fishing techniques do you mainly use to catch fish?

Multiple answers possible

<input type="checkbox"/> Pots and traps <input type="checkbox"/> <i>purse seine</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Demersal or bottom trawls (single rig, twin rig, quad rig)	<input type="checkbox"/> <i>nets</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Beam trawl (for shrimp and fish) <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____
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FISHING TIME

8. How many days do you fish on an annual basis?

.....

FISHING VESSEL

9. Can you tell us more about the vessel you are working on?

Vessel number*	Crew on board (number of people)	Size of the ship (meters)

** The **vessel number** that you provide will be used exclusively to determine who works together on the vessel. This allows us to take into account that some of the people surveyed are working on the same vessel. The information will be treated strictly confidentially and not be used for any other purposes. Your anonymity is guaranteed at all times.*

PART 3: PERSONAL EXPERIENCE WITH AND VIEW ON MARINE LITTER

10. Does marine litter cause problems for your work?

Please answer on the following scale, from value 1 meaning "totally disagree" to value 5 meaning "totally agree"

	1.Totally disagree	2.Somewhat disagree	3.Neither agree or disagree	4.Somewhat agree	5.Totally agree
Marine litter damages my propeller, equipment, and nets.					
Due to marine litter, I lose time since I have to clean my vessel, equipment and nets.					
Marine litter reduces fish catch (the amount, quality or the size)					

11. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following 7 statements?

Please tick one box for each row

	1.Totally disagree	2.Somewhat disagree	3.Neither agree or disagree	4.Somewhat agree	5.Totally agree
Marine litter is such an urgent problem for our marine ecosystems that we have to do something about it now					
Marine litter affects my earnings					
The effects of pollution on human health are worrisome					
Claims that current levels of pollution are severely					

threatening the seas are exaggerated					
I am willing to apply new techniques on my vessel to collect and monitor marine litter					
The fishing industry is an important source of today's marine litter problem					
Even if my contribution is small, it is important that I contribute in the effort to decrease marine litter					

PART 4: FISHING FOR LITTER

The Fishing for litter program seeks the contribution of the fisheries sector to the fight against marine litter. Special bags are provided to fishermen who are only required to do so to collect the garbage entangled in their nets in these bags. The rubbish is then recorded and recycled at the port.

12. Which conditions could make you decide to participate in Fishing for Litter?

Select a maximum of four conditions and rank them from 1 (most important) to 4 (least important)

- Under **no** circumstances
- Better facilities** to bring the collected marine litter back to the shore
- Better quality and varying sizes of **Big Bags**
- The introduction of a **special certificate/label** for fishers participating in Fishing for Litter
- Good **collaboration and communication** between the parties involved
- More **positive media attention** for the Fishing for Litter project
- The introduction of a **financial compensation** for catching and collecting marine litter
- Others (please specify).....

13. You have indicated that the introduction of a financial compensation for catching and collecting marine litter could make you decide to participate in Fishing for Litter in the future. What is the minimum amount per Big Bag (1 Big Bag = 1000 liter) you would like to receive in this case?

You can fill an amount here: €.....per bag

14. What is the reason why you are not willing to participate in Fishing for Litter?

You can tick more than one box

- It is (too) time consuming

- There is not much marine litter to collect
- I want to focus on catching fish only
- There is too much marine litter, a couple of ships that collect litter will not make a difference
- I have insufficient knowledge about the Fishing for Litter programme
- Other (please specify).....

15. The 7 statements that follow relate to Fishing for Litter. Please indicate on a scale from 1 (totally disagree) to 5 (totally agree) to what extent you agree with these statements.

Please tick one box for each row.

	1.Totally disagree	2.Somewhat disagree	3.Neither agree or disagree	4.Somewhat agree	5.Totally agree	I don't know
Collecting marine litter whilst fishing should be the norm	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People who are important to me - friends and family - would support my participation in FFL	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel a moral obligation to participate in FFL	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have enough time to collect and separate litter while I fish						
I trust that others will fish for litter	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

16. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following 7 statements?

Please tick one box for each row

	Totally disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Somewhat agree	Totally agree
There is a lot of litter concentrating in Crete coming from the Aegean Sea	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The island itself should protect its marine environment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fishing for litter in the Cretan coasts I contribute to the prevention of litter spreading to the rest of the Mediterranean	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

It would make me proud to offer to my land through the program	<input type="radio"/>				
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12. Would you participate in the Fishing for litter program if it was implemented in your location?

- Yes No

YOUR FEEDBACK

DO YOU HAVE ANY ADDITIONAL COMMENTS ABOUT THIS RESEARCH OR ABOUT MARINE LITTER IN GENERAL?

.....

THIS IS THE END OF THE SURVEY ~ WE THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR YOUR KIND COOPERATION IN THIS RESEARCH!

Appendix II

This appendix presents six tables, divided by area, on different types of statements relevant to the analysis of the research that were made by fishers during the dissemination of the questionnaire. Each section represents a different municipality to summarise the opinion of the locals. For example, topics such as their experience with marine litter, their relationship between fishers and local authorities or the relationship between fishers in the area were recorded. are seen as reasons to participate in a pro-environmental action are being recorded in the form of quotes in this section.

This appendix presents six tables, divided by area, that summarise statements made by local fishers on topics related to the analysis of this research. Topics such as the relationship between each other or their relationship with local authorities are examples of what has been recorded. The division of areas was made to help the reader understand the ongoing situation in each location. Some of the following quotes were used to support the quantitative data on the main body of this paper.

Heraklion

Marine litter in the area	
Marine litter excess	“ Sometimes litter is so much that one can say we need extra personnel to clean our nets.”

Marine litter excess	" People on the beach can not really see it, but once you go out in the open sea you can see huge piles of trash floating."
Many types of trash have been identified	"I have picked up all sorts of things from my net. From kids' toys and plastics to car parts and beach umbrellas."
Litter obstruct boat mobility	" When the sea is calm, the litter is much that I am afraid of passing through and risk getting my propeller stuck."
The situation in Heraklion is getting out of hand	"The situation in Heraklion is getting out of hand. I always let people know where I am when I fish because I had plastic clogging my propeller more than once."
Litter takes up fishers' time	" I have lost hours and days of fishing due to marine litter tangled in my nets."
Litter takes up fishers' time	" Sometimes we lose good days just because we have to clean and repair our nets. Marine litter is affecting us in all sorts of ways."
Litter effects on fish stocks	" I have caught fish that were distorted due to marine litter"
Litter effects on fish stocks	" I have seen so much litter that I am afraid of the quality of the fish I catch."
Relationship with other fishers	
Competition amongst fishers is high	"There is a lot of competition between us, no one in the port can deny it."
Trawlers increase competition	"Trawlers are our main competitor. They destroy everything on their way."
Trawlers increase competition	" Politicians and rich people own trawlers that make hundreds of thousands when we barely put a plate on our table."
Trawlers exploit the fish stocks	" Trawlers bear a lot of responsibility for the decreasing fish stock."
Competition amongst fishers is high	" The competition is high even between friends. The stock is decreasing each year."
Irresponsible actions of fishers	"Many fishers just leave damaged equipment in the sea."
Irresponsible actions of fishers	" Sometimes, I get disappointed. I see people abandoning nets in the sea, and then others pay the price when the nets get stacked on their propellers."
Fishers are becoming more aware	"In the past everyone used to throw their trash in the sea, nowadays this has changed."
Fishers are becoming more aware	"I always carry a bag for my trash when I depart, and I always empty it in the bin"

	when I return. Not many people do that here.”
Lack of trust between fishers	“ I do not trust other fishers as they talk too much but act little on the matter.”
Competition amongst fishers is high	“ We have to be competitive with each other; otherwise, we will not be able to cover our expenses.”
Relationship with the local authorities	
Disbelief in local authorities	“ I would never address local authorities to resolve an issue.”
Disbelief in local authorities	“ I feel they are all corrupted. If not, why so much injustice and pollution in the seas?”
Malfunctioning cleaning facilities	“ The organic cleaning facilities in the city do not even function anymore, and nobody knows about it. Imagine the impact that has on our sea.”
Hostile local authorities	“ I was once threatened by local authorities when I tried to report environmental crimes committed in the area.”
Disbelief in local authorities	“ Some things are so evident that it is unbelievable how no one is doing anything about it. I do not trust them.”
Hostile local authorities	“I have seen violations that I will put myself in a lot of danger if I decide to speak.”
Disbelief in local authorities and fishers	“ People bury their trash in beaches, and authorities know about it. I do not trust nor the authorities nor the people here.”
Comments on Fishing for Litter	
There is a need for financial aid	“ Professionals are just trying to make ends meet. A project that can financially assist that is very welcome.”
There is a need for financial aid	“ We need the extra money in order to bother cleaning. Our financial situation does not allow for voluntarism.”
FFL seems like an extra burden	“FFL sounds like new restrictions on a generation fighting for its survival.”
Bonus for fuel as an incentive	“ We do not necessarily need financial recompensation. However, a bonus for fuel or new nets can really motivate us to participate.”
Money as an incentive	“ We need incentives to activate ourselves. Money is the most effective one.”
Money as an incentive	“ If they can offer me money, I am up for it.”

FFL is not within fishers' responsibilities	"With all due respect, we are here to fish and feed our families. We are not here to clean the sea that others pollute."

Gazi

Marine litter in the area	
Marine litter excess due to currents	" Currents bring all sorts of trash from Heraklion."
Many types of trash have been identified	" I can go on for hours about the peculiar stuff I have found tangled in my nets."
Marine litter excess	" I wish I could say this part of the coast is clean."
Irresponsible actions due to lack of knowledge	" We used to treat the sea as an infinite landfill. We did not know. Now that we see the results, we are starting to change."
Relationship with other fishers	
Good relationship amongst fishers	" We have a good relationship with each other because we are only a few here, but competition is inevitable."
Good relationship amongst fishers	" We are all friends here. It is some sort of protection. Imagine a rivalry in a port of 15 boats. That can not be good for us."
Irresponsible actions due to lack of education	" We need better education. I have seen people throwing all sorts of things while in the open sea."
Relationship with the local authorities	
Lacking support from the authorities	" We lack the necessary support. We have a small port that is very neglected."
Fishers' demands are not being heard	" I have complained many times for the condition of the port, but I was never heard. I would not describe them as attentive."
Fishers' demands are not being heard	" Seals and dolphins destroy our nets, and nobody protects us from them. There are laws that protect those species but no law that recompensates me for the damages they provoke."
Fishers' demands are not being heard	" We demand support for the damages sea mammals do to us. I am tired of repairing my nets because of dolphins."
Comments on Fishing for Litter	
Conscience is required for FFL to succeed	" The FFL is not enough to clean the sea. We also need a conscience."

Money as an incentive	" I do not see why not participate, but I need the extra money to keep on doing it on a steady basis."
Money as an incentive	" If there is money involved, I am definitely participating in something like this."

Hersonissos

Marine litter in the area	
Tourism as the primary source of pollution	" Tourism is destroying the area. Simple as that."
Tourism as the primary source of pollution	"This is a very touristic area. All the coast is filled with bars and restaurants that dispose of all their waste in the sea."
Unattended infrastructure leads to pollution	" The coast is filled with tunnels that drive water currents from the mountains to the sea. If one pays them a visit, he will see that they are blocked from the piles of trash that end up in the sea when the first rains come."
Comments on Fishing for Litter	
Bonus for fuel as an incentive	" We prefer money for fuel as an incentive to participate."
Tax for plastic bags as a financing mechanism	" The tax for plastic bags can be an intelligent way to finance this project."
There is no reason why not to participate	" I see no reason why not to participate. This project is only good news for us."
Money as an incentive	" What fishers need is an incentive. Something that will get them started. It can be 5€ or 55€ per bag. The important thing is to get them started so that they can see what they can actually achieve if they try."

Ierapetra

Marine litter in the area	
Trade ships as a source of pollution	" Trade ships are an important source of pollution in the area. A lot of them pass from this area crossing the southeast Mediterranean."
Greenhouses as a source of pollution	" In Ierapetra we have a lot of greenhouses. The ones built close to the sea are using the sea as their disposal area. A lot of fishers have had problems with greenhouse

	plastics tangled in their nets and propellers.”
Greenhouses as a source of pollution	“ Here, we mostly find litter coming from greenhouses and local people. Currents do not really affect this part of the island. At least not in that way.”
Chemicals waste from boats as a source of pollution	“ The chemicals we use to clean our boats are really harmful to the sea.”
Relationship with other fishers	
Lack of trust amongst fishers	“ Do not trust what they tell you. People here do not even consider the environment.”
Lack of trust amongst fishers	“ People here call me an ecologist. Sometimes they pass next to me while I fish and throw plastic in the sea just to make me angry and have fun with me. That is the level of respect fishers have for the sea here.”
Competition amongst fishers is high	“ We tend to be competitive, and that concludes in overfishing.”
Competition amongst fishers is high	“ If people know that I had a good catch in a specific spot today, they will probably be there really early tomorrow. People are hungry, and competition is high.”
Relationship with local authorities	
The municipality is trying to help with the issue	“The municipality put someone to fish litter in the port, which is helpful.”
Excellent relationship with local authorities	“ We have an excellent relationship with local authorities. They listen to our demands, and we listen to theirs.”
Malfunctioning cleaning facilities	“Organic cleaning facilities do not really work in the area. If you combine this with the pollution greenhouses do to the area, it is a big problem. Authorities have to act.”
Fishers’ demands are not being heard	“ We have reported greenhouses throwing trash in the sea plenty of times. Why does the municipality keep on ignoring the issue?”
Comments on Fishing for Litter	
Money as an incentive	“I do not need to hear more. If there is financial compensation per bag, I will clean the whole area by myself.”
Money as an incentive to alleviate injustice	“ I know there are a lot of things that can come out of this, but with the injustice fishers face every day, money would be the only reason that can convince us to do that.”

Money in exchange with fishers' efforts	" We need something in exchange to do that. Time, fuel and effort will be invested from our side."
Good instalments are required	"We will need big trashcans to dispose of the litter and carefully put around the port so that we do not put much effort into it."

Rethimno

Marine litter in the area	
Marine litter is present	" Noone can say that he never had an incident with marine litter."
Tourism and locals as a source of pollution	" Rethimnon is a coastal city; thus, it suffers from the thoughtlessness of its citizens and tourism."
Tourism as a source of pollution	" Hotels are polluting a lot. Not only through waste disposal but from attracting more tourist each year. The pandemic has shown to us the damage tourism did to the sea the previous years."
Tourism as a source of pollution	" Bars, restaurants and hotels are constantly polluting. The litter we catch can prove that."
Relationship with other fishers	
Competition amongst fishers is high	"There is a lot of competition between us. The profession is not as it used to be."
Competition amongst fishers is high due to lack of education	"We argue and we fight. I think it is because of the lack of education in this profession. Most fishers I know never went to school."
Lack of knowledge affects trust amongst fishers	" We lack the knowledge in my opinion. That is why we blame each other instead of doing something."
Trawlers increase competition	"Trawlers are killing small-scale fishers. They violate the law while they overfish the already decreasing stock."
Relationship with local authorities	
Good relations with local authorities	" I never had a problem with local authorities."
Lack of support due to political problems	" Political problems in the country also affect fishers. We don not receive the support we deserve."
Malfunctioning cleaning facilities	"I believe that cleaning facilities malfunction in Rethimnon. I do not let my

	children near the organic cleaning facilities for example.”
Lack of support from local authorities	“Our nets get damaged from alien species and no one is helping us.”
NGOs are not welcome in the area	“NGOs create problems to receive money from donors and the state. I do not want anything to do with NGOs anymore.”
NGOs are not welcome in the area	“ There is a lot of suspicion for NGOs. Everybody gets involved with the sea but with no outcome. So why would I trust them?”
Comments on Fishing for Litter	
Lack of willingness to participate due to lack of support	“Fishers are being neglected, so why would they help?”
Lack of trust in NGOs to implement the program	“Many organisations have come in Rethimnon to implement a project, and then we never saw them again. I do not want that to happen again.”
Good instalments are required	“We need to make sure that bins will be put close to our boats and that the program will be taking care of them. Otherwise, it will not succeed.”
Respectful reward as an incentive	“ I do not necessarily need a large amount of money to participate. I just need a reward that shows that my effort to protect the environment is being respected.”
There is a need for financial aid	“The fish stock is so decreased that an extra income would be great.”
Good instalments are required	“We need good instalments. I do not want to waste more time carrying trash around the port. The program has to take care of that.”

Agios Nikolaos

Marine litter in the area	
Locals are more disrespectful than the tourists	“Locals are disrespectful to the sea. In comparison to the tourists that visit us, we lack education.”

Locals are more disrespectful than the tourists	"Marine litter is a problem of the local people. This is a touristic area, and I see tourists treating the place better than locals do."
Relationship with other fishers	
Decreasing stocks increase competition	"There is a lot of competition between us as the stocks are constantly decreasing. It is getting so hard that even hobbyists are also damaging our earnings."
Claims of high competition are exaggerated	"We are not as competitive as one may expect. Most of us know each other for years and have developed good relationships."
Good relationship amongst fishers	"I know most of the guys here, and I cannot remember having any problem with anyone. The job is getting harder, but we do not blame each other."
Comments on Fishing for Litter	
FFL seems like an extra burden	"New projects will create new problems and obstacles. I am very sceptical, and I believe we would probably be better off without them."
Lack of trust in NGOs to implement the program	"I believe NGOs are lying to us, and therefore, I would prefer a project like this to be implemented by a different carrier."
There is a need for financial aid	"I do not expect a project like this to change my financial situation, but a small income would make me like what I do."
FFL is not within fishers' responsibilities	"My job is not to pick up trash from the sea. My job is hard and dangerous. I would not do something like this for free."

Appendix III

The following table demonstrates the operationalisation of the conceptual framework of this research. The multiple selection questions are not included in this table due to practical inconvenience.

Theory	Variable	Indicator	Survey questions
	Perceived behavioural control	Perception of competence to achieve a goal	I have enough time to collect and separate litter while I fish

Theory of Planned Behaviour	Subjective norm	Social pressure on fishing sector	People who are important to me - friends and family - would support my participation in FFL
	Attitude	Social pressure on fishers	Collecting marine litter whilst fishing should be the norm
Value-Belief-Norm Theory	Biospheric values	Fishers' concern for the sea environment	Claims that current levels of pollution are severely threatening the seas are exaggerated
	Altruistic values	Fishers' concern for marine life and other people	The effects of pollution on human health are worrisome
	Egoistic values	Fishers' concern for personal sources	Marine litter damages my propeller, equipment, and nets.
			Due to marine litter, I lose time since I have to clean my vessel, equipment and nets.
			Marine litter reduces fish catch (the amount, quality or the size)
			Marine litter affects my earnings
	Openness to change behaviour		I am willing to apply new techniques on my vessel to collect and monitor marine litter
	Awareness of consequences	Fishers consider marine litter a threat	Marine litter is such an urgent problem for our marine ecosystems that we have to do something about it now
	Ascription of responsibility	Fishers believe they can bring change to the issue	The fishing industry is an important source of today's marine litter problem
Even if my contribution is small, it is important that I contribute in the effort to decrease marine litter			
Personal norm	Sense of obligation to address the issue	I feel a moral obligation to participate in FFL	
Benefits	Label	The introduction of a special certificate/label for fishers participating in Fishing for Litter as a condition to participate	

		Public promotions	More positive media attention for the Fishing for Litter project as a condition to participate
		Financial/Non-financial compensation	The introduction of a financial compensation for catching and collecting marine litter project as a condition to participate
	Island geographic characteristics		There is a lot of litter concentrating in Crete coming from the Aegean Sea
			The island itself should protect its marine environment
			Fishing for litter in the Cretan coasts I contribute to the prevention of litter spreading to the rest of the Mediterranean
Trust in others		I trust that others will fish for litter	
Pride		It would make me proud to offer to my land through the program	